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High-speed Digital Image Correlation (DIC) for measuring deformation and vibration of fast rotating fan blades

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Abstract. Due to ecological requirements, the bypass-ratio of future civil turbofan engines will be increased. This leads to ultra-high bypass ratio (UHBR) engines, which bring in new challenges concerning the blade material, structural integration, and aeroelastic behaviour of the fan. The ambition of the project Composite fan Aerodynamic, Aeroelastic, and Aeroacoustic Validation Rig (CA3ViAR) is to design and test an open-test-case fan that experiences instability mechanisms, which are representative for UHBR fans of civil aircrafts. The optical measurement technique Digital Image Correlation (DIC) allows for the spatial measurement of deformations. The aim is to apply this technique to measure rotor blade deformation under loading and its vibration due to aeroelastic phenomena to get a better understanding of the structural and aeroelastic behaviour of the composite fan. However, the high rotational speeds, blade vibration frequencies, and expected amplitudes pose challenges for the measurement setup. In this work, a high-speed DIC system is prepared and tested to measure deformation and vibration of a fast rotating blade. Additionally, the requirements for the DIC setup are defined and presented. The expected blade tip speeds in the CA3ViAR project are up to 295 m/s and the blade frequencies of interest up to 650 Hz. Therefore, particular emphasis must be given to the setup in order to eliminate motion blur due to the rotation and to achieve the required frequency. This leads to a setup with synchronised high-speed cameras and a laser to measure frequency vibrations up to 1 kHz with an exposure time below 210 ns. Test measurements are conducted on a stationary beam and an axial blower with a max. blade tip speed of 50 m/s. A data analysis method is developed and described to eliminate the rigid body rotation, analyse the deformation of each blade compared to a reference condition, and analyse the spatial vibration in the frequency domain for a high number of data points per time step. The results of the structural beam are in agreement with the reference measurements and numerical simulations. By analysing the spatial vibration modes of the axial blower, the 1F-flap mode is identified at 38 Hz. In conclusion, this DIC setup shows promising results for future deformation and vibration measurements on a scaled UHBR fan.

Introduction

The design of UHBR engines trend to shortened intakes and slender as well as highly loaded fan blades made of composite materials. These impose new challenges regarding the structural integration of the blades and their aeroelastic behaviour, e.g. vibration due to increased inlet distortion and risk of flutter [1]. The ambition of the CA3ViAR project is to design a fan stage that experiences instability mechanisms, which are representative for UHBR

fans. Comprehensive experimental investigation will be performed to measure aerodynamic, aeroelastic and aeroacoustic performance in a wide range of operating conditions. The final objective of the project is to provide an open test case for the entire research community, including geometrical data as well as numerical and experimental results.

To measure the structural behaviour of the fan blade, common measurement techniques are strain gauges (SG) and blade tip timing (BTT). Here, the DIC method offers further potential for the identification of unsteady and continuous deformation on the entire blade surface. DIC optically measures displacements with a high spatial resolution and accuracy. In the procedure, at least two cameras are used, which record a random speckle pattern on the surface to be examined. The pattern enables a correlation of corresponding points in the images and thus a triangulation of the 3D position. The basic principle of the method is described in [2]. For rotating objects, vibrations have been measured on wind turbine blades [3] and helicopter models [4]. Furthermore, spatial deformation of a V2500 engine fan blade has been measured and compared to numerical simulation [5]. A random speckle pattern was projected on a specific circumferential position, allowing the deformation measurement of a single blade to be taken at this circumferential position. The aim in this study is to prepare and test a new high-speed DIC setup to measure time-resolved deformation of the CA3ViAR rotor blades, capturing the full rotor and resolving the structural mode vibration prone to aeroelastic phenomena.

Target measurements and resulting setup requirements

For the measurements in the CA3ViAR project, several structural parameters are of special concern due to the slender blades, the composite material, and the desired instabilities. For the DIC measurements, the goal is to measure blade geometry under loading, hot-to-cold shape transformation, and vibration due to forced response and flutter. In addition to the measurement targets, the measurement object, in this case the CA3ViAR rotor, defines the setup requirements. The details, design, and the expected aeroelastic phenomena of the fan are described in [1] and [6]. Important parameters are given in Tab. 1. The resulting fan tip speed of 295 m/s at cruise

Table 1: FAN DESIGN PARAMETERS

	reference fan	scaled CA3ViAR fan	
Operating point	cruise	cruise	take-off
Rot. speed n / RPM	2375	8667	8095
Fan tip speed V_{Θ} / (m/s)	272	295	275
Fan tip radius r_{tip} / m	1.093	0.325	0.325

condition for the scaled fan requires short exposure times to eliminate motion blur. The exposure time has to be chosen to reduce the object movement dp_{max} below 1 px within the exposure time. The max. exposure time $t_{max.exp}$ can be estimated with

$$fov = \frac{l_D b_S}{f}, \quad Af = \frac{fov}{n_{px}}, \quad t_{max.exp} = \frac{dp_{max}}{v_I},$$

including the focal length f , the distance to the object l_D , and the sensor size b_S . The field of view and the pixel of the camera n_{px} allows for the calculation of the resolution Af of the object on the image. The image velocity v_I in px/s can be calculated by the ratio of fan tip speed V_{Θ} and the resolution Af , which is used to calculate the max. exposure time $t_{max.exp}$ dependent on the allowed object movement dp_{max} . With the given parameters, the maximum exposure time must be below 2.15 μ s.

To resolve the blade vibration, the sampling frequency must be at least two times the highest

vibration frequency of interest, based on the Nyquist-Shannon theorem. The first two modes of the rotor are expected to experience vibration due to flutter or forced response. The maximum frequency (mode 2, max. rotational speed) is expected to be below 700 Hz, leading to a required sampling frequency above 1400 Hz. The maximum allowed vibration amplitude during measurement should not exceed 1 mm, which is estimated using structural simulation and a superposition of static stress and modal deformation including safety factors. Therefore, the DIC-system should be able to resolve vibration amplitudes below 1 mm.

Experimental setup

Measurement hardware

Based on the identified requirements, two high-speed cameras (Photron SA-X2 and Photron SA-3) and a pulsed high-speed laser (Terra PIV 527-100-M) are used. The cameras provide a resolution of 1 MPx and a combined frame rate of 2 kHz. The laser has a pulse rate of up to 10 kHz with a pulse duration below 210 ns. The laser is used to expose the rotating object to reduce exposure time and improve the synchronisation of both cameras.

Test case - Bending beam

First, the high-speed setup is validated during vibration tests on a bending beam. The tested beam is fixed on a bench and is 100 mm wide, 3 mm thick and has a height of 100 mm between bench and tip. The setup is shown in Fig. 1a. The cameras are equipped with 50 mm lenses

(a) Bending beam

(b) Axial blower

Figure 1: Experimental setup of test cases

and synchronised with the laser. The laser light is expanded by two biconcave lenses with a combined focal length of $f = -19$ mm. This allows the laser to illuminate the entire bending beam surface. A speckle pattern on printed foil with 1.5 mm dot diameter is applied to the surface of the bending beam, resulting in a 5 px dot on the camera sensor. The bending beam is equipped with a laser distance sensor (LDS) and an accelerometer, both sampled with a data acquisition triggered by the cameras.

Test case - Axial blower

After the validation of the setup during the stationary bending beam test, the setup is tested to measure deformation and vibration on an axial blower during operation. The blower has five blades with a diameter of 0.99 m and a hub-to-tip ratio of 0.3. The maximum rotational speed is 960 rpm, resulting in a tip speed of 50 m/s. The speckle pattern is applied by printed foils on each blade and the spinner with a dot diameter of 5 mm on the foil and 5 px on the image. The blower and the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1b, including the two high-speed cameras and laser.

Figure 2: Procedure to analyse DIC data on rotating object

Data analysis

The spatial analysis of deformation and vibration requires several data processes. The procedure developed in this work is shown in Fig. 2. The common DIC data procedure of calibration, correlation, and triangulation are performed in the commercial software *Vic-3D 8*. The resulting position in reference condition $(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z})$ and their displacement $(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W})$ over time are in camera coordinates $(CS)_C$ and exported to *MATLAB*. Here, the data is transformed to the rotor coordinate system and rigid body rotation is removed using least-squares method with data points on the spinner, which have no deformation expected. This allows to analyse out-of-plane (OoP) and IP deformation.

Results

The following section presents the results of the tests at the bending beam and axial blower.

Bending beam

First, the high-speed setup is tested on a bending beam to show the general applicability to measure displacements and vibration. The bending beam is forced in vibration by an impulsive excitation, and the free vibration is measured. In addition to the DIC system, a LDS is measuring the OoP deformation, and an accelerometer is placed on the top right corner of the bending beam, measuring the acceleration. The resulting displacement is shown in Fig. 3 for two different time intervals. The grey area illustrates the uncertainties defined by the linearity error of the LDS for the given measurement setup. The measured displacements by the DIC system are within the uncertainties of the LDS. The displacements are still captured well within amplitudes below 0.25 mm, however, the noise levels are increased.

The data is transformed in the frequency domain to analyse the vibration. In Fig. 4, the resulting amplitude over the frequency is shown. The DIC data is extracted at the position of the accelerometer at the top right corner of the bending beam. The uncertainty of the accelerometer is given as the 95% confidence interval in grey. The first peak is found at 32 Hz in both measurement data and the DIC amplitude of 0.49 mm is in the uncertainty of the accelerometer. A second and third peak is found at 189 Hz and 209 Hz in the DIC data and confirmed by the accelerometer, with a difference below 1 Hz in frequency and 6 μm in amplitude. Three peaks found by the DIC system between 95 Hz and 175 Hz are not based on the beam

Figure 3: Comparison of OoP displacement between DIC (red) and LDS (black) measurement, grey area illustrates uncertainties of LDS

Figure 4: Comparison of vibration amplitude over frequency between DIC (red) and accelerometer (black), grey area illustrates 95% confidence interval of accelerometer

structure and therefore also not measured by the accelerometer. The resulting vibration patterns over the full surface are shown in Fig. 5 and compared to the modes from a modal analysis using FEM. The patterns align in amplitude distribution over the surface. However, increased noise is present for patterns at high frequency due to the low vibration amplitude.

Axial blower

An axial blower is used to test the high-speed DIC setup for rotational objects. Measurements for different speeds and conditions are tested. Figure 6a shows the rotational speeds and the resulting deformation at the blade tip of one blade in reference to the unloaded condition. The deformation depends on the rotational speed as expected. An increased deformation is measured for higher rotational speeds. By operating the blower at constant rotational speed, the mean deformation is constant, superposed with a blade vibration. For measurement 3, the blower is rapidly shut off after 0.1s measurement time. Thus, the rotational speed and deformation

Figure 5: Comparison of DIC vibration patterns and FEM mode shapes

(a) Deformation of the blade tip for different rotational speeds (b) Extracted frequency response at the blade tip of measurement 3

Figure 6: Point deformation data of the axial blower from DIC measurement

is reduced. Furthermore, due to the rapid shut off, there is a forced excitation and the blade vibration is increased. The resulting frequency response at the blade tip is shown in Fig. 6b, including several peaks at specific frequencies. The spatial pattern is extracted and shown for frequencies of 12 Hz, 37 Hz, and 66 Hz. Figure 7 shows the real part of the extracted complex amplitudes for different phase angles at 12 Hz. The pattern reveals a rigid-body gyration of the rotor, without noticeable deformation of the blades itself. This structural behaviour is expected to be based on the elasticity of the bearing housing of the rotor. The pattern at 38 Hz, shown for different phase angles in Fig. 8, is in line with an expected first flap mode (1F) of the rotor blades. Furthermore, the neighbouring blades vibrate out of phase similar to a nodal diameter 2. The vibration is captured well and with a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), despite the low maximum amplitude of 0.1 mm. A more complex pattern is extracted at 66 Hz, shown for

Figure 7: Vibration pattern at 12 Hz for different phase angles

Figure 8: Vibration pattern at 38 Hz for different phase angles

different phase angles in Fig. 9. Based on the pattern, a superposition of the first torsional (1T) and the second flap (2F) mode is assumed. However, a modal analysis is required to identify true mode shapes.

Conclusions and Outlook

A high-speed DIC setup has been tested and successfully measured deformation and vibration of a bending beam and axial blower. The setup consists of two high-speed cameras and a laser, allowing synchronised measurements with a frame rate up to 2 kHz. Due to the laser illumination, the exposure time is short enough to suppress motion blur. The laser light intensity proved to be sufficient to illuminate a rotor diameter of 1 m. A data analysis method is presented to analyse 3D deformation on rotating surfaces in time and frequency domain of a large number of data points. The spatial information visualises the structural dynamics and allows for a detailed interpretation of the measured vibration.

The system will be used in the CA3ViAR measurements and the resulting data compared to strain gauges and blade tip timing measurements. An application of the speckle pattern with fluorescent paint will be used to improve the pattern contrast and eliminate laser light reflection.

Figure 9: Vibration pattern at 66 Hz for different phase angles

An exchange of the Photron SA-3 with an improved high-speed camera could update the setup to a frame rate of 10 kHz with the given laser. Also future high-speed cameras with higher image resolution can improve the measured spatial resolution and accuracy.

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